

Teacher Training in Hybrid Learning Environments: Artificial Intelligence, Ethics and Socioemotional Aspects in the Digital Material Production Course

Andromeda Goretti de Menezes Campos¹, Talita Molina Lopes Tanes¹

¹ Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Espírito Santo, Brazil

Email: andromeda.campos@ifes.edu.br, talitatanes@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15847232>

Abstract

This paper discusses the development of the Digital Material Production course for educators, conducted in the first semester of 2025. In this iteration, the project "Potentialities of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education" served as its backbone, differentiating it from previous editions. With a central theme that was both comprehensive and engaging, the course aimed to equip students with knowledge about the use of AI in education, explore generative AI tools for digital material production, understand the ethical and responsible use of these technologies, and foster greater engagement in both in-person and remote settings. The project was structured into three stages: (1) an introduction to learning theories and instructional design models; (2) hands-on production of digital educational materials using AI tools; and (3) a final seminar where students presented their outputs and participated in discussions on AI ethics, copyright, and social inclusion. A comparative analysis of the educational materials produced indicated a qualitative improvement, with students demonstrating a deeper understanding of AI ethics. Furthermore, the number of students attending more than 60% of in-person classes increased by 13.33% compared to the previous cohort, suggesting a higher level of engagement fostered by the hybrid model. However, participation in the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) was lower than expected. This could be attributed to factors such as difficulties with digital literacy, a common challenge in online learning environments. This experience reinforces the transformative potential of AI in education, provided that it is balanced with ethical awareness and socioemotional competencies. The findings highlight the need for adaptive pedagogical strategies that effectively integrate AI, ensuring inclusivity and promoting the reflective and responsible use of technology in teaching and learning processes.

Keywords: Socioemotional; AI; Ethics; Teacher Training.

1 Introduction

The transformations brought about by digital technologies in education have intensified with the expansion of Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly generative AI. Tools such as ChatGPT, DALL-E, Perplexity, and other multimodal interfaces have directly impacted school routines, from content production to learning mediation. These advances challenge educators and institutions to reconfigure not only their pedagogical practices but also their conceptions of the teaching role, knowledge, and learning itself (Luckin et al., 2016; Holmes et al., 2019; Huang et al., 2023).

Despite the promises of personalization, automation, and increased efficiency in education promoted by AI (Zhao et al., 2022), studies show that its implementation in educational settings requires ethical, epistemological, and pedagogical care. Uncritical adoption of technologies may reinforce social inequalities, deepen human detachment in educational processes, and compromise fundamental educational principles such as equity, authorship, and the holistic development of learners (Borenstein & Howard, 2021; Amaral et al., 2022; Moura et al., 2022).

In this context, teacher education emerges as a central axis. Teachers need not only to understand how AI tools operate but also to develop a critical and ethical stance toward the social, political, and emotional impacts of this technology in educational contexts (Becker & Marques, 2001; Franco et al., 2006; Silva et al., 2022). Some

studies highlight that many educators still feel unprepared to face these challenges, mainly due to a lack of continuing education that integrates theory, practice, and ethical reflection (Holmes et al., 2019; Franco et al., 2006; Amaral et al., 2022).

The ethics of AI use in education, in turn, has been extensively discussed in the scientific literature. Issues related to algorithmic transparency, data privacy, intellectual property, and systemic biases embedded in AI-trained datasets are identified as central to the responsible implementation of these technologies (Borenstein & Howard, 2021; Amaral et al., 2022). Furthermore, the emergence of increasingly autonomous systems, capable of making decisions based on opaque criteria, raises concerns about the dehumanization of pedagogical relationships and the marginalization of dissenting voices (Huang et al., 2023; Holmes et al., 2019).

Alongside technical and ethical debates, another field has gained prominence: affectivity and the socio-emotional aspects of technology-mediated education. According to Henri Wallon (1968) and Jean Piaget (2014), affectivity is an essential component of the teaching-learning process, as it mobilizes students' motivation, will, interest, and engagement. When neglected, especially in remote or hybrid contexts, it can undermine the bond between teacher and student, increase feelings of loneliness, and promote dropout (Blando et al., 2023; Vieira et al., 2022; Trierweiler, 2024).

Case studies reveal that often invisible affective difficulties directly impact students' academic performance and their sense of belonging within the university environment. Factors such as insecurity, lack of motivation, insufficient institutional support, and distant teacher-student relationships are identified as barriers to meaningful learning (Silva et al., 2022; Blando et al., 2023; Jacques et al., 2015). These findings highlight the need for teacher education to also include the development of socio-emotional skills, such as empathy, active listening, emotional support, and conflict mediation.

In the case of Distance Education (DE), these demands become even more urgent. Brazilian literature on DE indicates that, despite technological advancements, many programs still maintain an instructorist logic focused on content transmission, disregarding dialogical mediation and student care (Franco et al., 2006; Kieling Franco et al., 2006). Research shows that affectivity in DE is directly related to academic success, student retention, and the quality of the educational experience (Marcilio et al., 2023; Vieira et al., 2022; Moura et al., 2022).

Still within this context, Villas-Boas (2019) argues that there is a rupture of previously consolidated concepts and models, requiring teachers to confront new challenges and complex dilemmas. In this scenario, educators seek to develop strategies to present knowledge meaningfully in the classroom, considering that students access information through the internet in various contexts; they promote initiatives to stimulate reading and efficient study practices, even in an environment characterized by the constant presence of digital media; and they strive to integrate knowledge and skills development with the technologies available, aiming to foster lasting learning.

Thus, there is a need for the training of education professionals who are practically familiar with Active Learning (AL) strategies and methods, as they support students' active engagement in their learning processes, reduce dropout and retention rates, stimulate greater student autonomy, create learning environments where students are required to use higher-order thinking skills (analyze, synthesize, create (ANDERSON et al., 2001)), and contribute to the development of more creative teachers.

Given these challenges, this article aims to present and analyze the formative experience, that is, a structured and intentional educational approach aimed at fostering critical thinking, ethical awareness, and socioemotional development, offered through the course Production of Digital Materials, conducted in the first semester of 2025, as part of the Technical Program in Educational Multimedia, offered through distance

learning with mandatory in-person meetings, at the Federal Institute of Espírito Santo. Unlike previous editions, this version was structured based on active learning, with the central theme "Potentialities of Generative AI in Education," integrating the following areas: theoretical foundations of learning, active learning for the production of digital educational materials (DEM) with and without AI, and ethical and socio-emotional discussions on its educational application. The course was designed not only to develop technical skills but also to foster an ethical, reflective, and affective attitude in the use of technologies and in the interpersonal relationships involved in the teaching and learning process, contributing to a more integrated teacher education aligned with contemporary challenges.

2 Research Design

This section describes the methodological choices adopted for the development of the study, considering the justifications that motivated its implementation and its contributions based on the results obtained.

The research presented is descriptive in nature, as it is based on the researchers' prior knowledge of the investigated issue. A qualitative-quantitative methodological approach was adopted, integrating quantitative and qualitative aspects in a complementary manner. The quantitative dimension is reflected in the analysis of numerical data, which allows the measurement of results and the identification of objective patterns. The qualitative dimension, on the other hand, is essential for gaining a deeper understanding of the perceptions and experiences of the individuals directly involved in the studied context, enabling a more sensitive and contextualized interpretation of the investigated reality.

The main data collection techniques adopted in this study were observation, questionnaires, and document analysis. Non-structured observation was chosen, prioritizing a spontaneous and natural approach, which allowed for more authentic immersion in the investigated environment. To systematically record these observations, a field diary was used to document students' behaviors, reactions, and attitudes individually, aiming to contribute to the validation of the initial hypothesis. Observation, in this sense, proves to be a valuable tool for capturing aspects of reality that cannot be apprehended solely through questionnaires or documents, as it enables the analysis of phenomena in their concreteness, at the time and place in which they occur (Deslandes, 2007).

The questionnaire was used because, according to Gil (2010), as a data collection instrument, it offers significant advantages, such as ensuring the anonymity of responses, providing respondents with the flexibility to participate at a convenient time, and reducing the influence of interpersonal factors, such as the researcher's presence or the interviewee's characteristics. In this study, the questionnaire aimed to capture students' perceptions regarding the transversal use of affectivity in the teaching and learning process, as well as their perceptions of the effectiveness of the methodology applied.

Document analysis was necessary because, throughout the course offering, attendance at in-person sessions was recorded, access to Moodle and to each element within the Virtual Learning Environment (VLE) was logged (by student), and problem-solving activities were posted, analyzed, resolved, and evaluated, generating documents containing students' grades and responses. Stake (1995) attributes a complementary role to document analysis relative to other sources of evidence, highlighting its relevance especially in contexts where direct observation is not possible. According to the author, documents can provide valuable information that contributes to understanding the investigated phenomenon, serving, in some cases, as substitutes for experiences not directly witnessed by the researchers.

Finally, the results were analyzed from the perspectives of both the students and the instructors and are discussed in the following sections of this paper.

3 Course Methodology (ADDIE + Active Learning + Socio-emotional axis)

According to Gava, Nobre, and Sondermann (2014), the planning and implementation of courses across various programs must be carried out in an integrated manner and contextualized to students' everyday experiences. Particularly in Distance Education (DE), such planning must be highly detailed, especially when utilizing a Virtual Learning Environment (VLE).

For the development of the Production of Digital Materials course, the ADDIE Model was employed, as it is a widely used instructional design methodology that aligns with the institution's specificities. In the specific case of this course's production, the authors possessed the necessary expertise and assumed the following roles: Instructor 1 served as the instructional designer, content specialist, teacher educator, and online tutor; Instructor 2 served as the instructional designer, pedagogical specialist, and text editor. Figure 1 presents the ADDIE Model, its phases, and the description of the actions undertaken in each phase.

ADDIE Model			
	Phase	Question	Actions
Concep- tion	Analysis	Understand the task to be performed	Define: • Target audience • Learning context • Learning goals Consider: • Resources • Infrastructure • Deadlines
	Design	Structuring the Material	Define: • Learning objectives • Media to be used • Evaluation methods
	Development	Producing the Material	Produce: • Designed materials
Executi- on	Implementation	Validating the Material	Perform: • Validation tests • Implementation of the material
	Evaluation	Evaluating the Material	Evaluation • Ongoing, throughout the project • Final, with the material users

Figure 1. ADDIE Model. Adapted from Gava, Nobre, and Sondermann (2014).

Based on the proposal presented by Gava, Nobre, and Sondermann (2014), the ADDIE Model can be structured into two main blocks: Design and Implementation. This organization aims to systematize the stages involved in the development of educational materials, contributing to coherence between pedagogical objectives, methodologies, and the resources adopted.

Drawing on the data gathered during the analysis phase, a pedagogical plan was developed for the course content, including the systematic definition of learning objectives, the organization of content and activities, and the design of assessment methods. In addition, the media and technologies most appropriate to the identified context were selected, ensuring coherence among educational elements and enhancing the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process. The course methodology for Production of Digital Materials was thus defined for implementation in the first semester of 2025. Subsequently, in line with the ADDIE framework, the educational materials were developed according to the previously established plan.

To design the methodology to be applied in the course, the team evaluated recurring issues observed in previous editions, such as student failures, low participation in face-to-face sessions, and limited engagement in the virtual learning environment. This was coupled with students' concerns—many of whom are practicing educators—regarding the operation of AI tools and the need for a critical and ethical stance on the social, political, and emotional impacts of such technologies in education. Another important factor was the need to

prepare education professionals to design digital educational materials and to develop competencies for working with active learning methodologies in hybrid learning environments.

3.1 Theoretical Content Development: Production of Digital Materials

With regard to the theoretical content—or content that was not part of the active methodology proposed in this study—the course included the following topics: Educational Resource Development, Media for Distance Education, Digital Educational Materials (DEMs), and a reflection on their implications for education.

Students also explored Learning Theories and Learning Styles with the aim of providing a theoretical foundation for the development of Digital Educational Materials. In addition, they engaged with, in order to assimilate and apply, the potential of Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) in education.

Assessments for these topics were conducted online, asynchronously, and individually—differently from the problem-based learning (PBL) tasks. For the theoretical content, traditional questionnaires were used. However, when assessing the “problem situations,” the application of concepts was evaluated in practice, based on pre-established criteria using rubrics.

3.2 Development of the Active Methodology for the Course “Production of Digital Materials”

Problem-based learning (PBL) scenarios were used as the active methodology, with components developed both in-person and remotely. The choice of this format aimed to enhance students’ sense of belonging to the institution, as teamwork fosters relationships among students and between students and the instructor. Active learning also promotes autonomy, stimulates critical thinking, strengthens problem-solving skills, values collaborative work, and enhances students’ adaptability—preparing them to face real-life challenges.

The PBL scenarios explored by the 17 students enrolled in this course were structured as follows:

- **Central Theme:** The Potential of Generative Artificial Intelligence in Education.
- **Subthemes:** Intelligent Tutoring Systems; Educational Chatbots; Personalized Learning; Artificial Intelligence and Inclusion in Education; Ethics and Artificial Intelligence in Education; and Artificial Intelligence in Early Childhood Education.
- **Team Size:** Maximum of 5 students.
- **Target Audience:** Defined according to each scenario.
- **Resolution Time:** 1 to 2 weeks (depending on complexity).
- **Number of PBL Scenarios:** 5.
- **Educational Materials Developed:** Infographic, Animation, Podcast, Video Lesson, and Recorded Slide Presentation.

For the development of the problem scenarios, the authors used ChatGPT, following the construction of a specific prompt designed for this purpose. An example of a problem scenario explored in the “Production of Digital Materials” course is presented below:

Problem-Based Scenario:

You have been invited to develop a Digital Educational Material for 2nd-year high school students at a private school located in an urban area in Brazil. The school adopts active learning methodologies and is currently carrying out an interdisciplinary project on “Ethics and Artificial Intelligence in Education.”

Target Audience Characteristics:

- *Students aged 16 to 17, with strong proficiency in digital technologies (frequent use of smartphones, social media, online educational platforms, and research tools).*
- *They have a basic familiarity with the concept of Artificial Intelligence but only an initial understanding of its ethical implications.*
- *They show high potential for engaging in debate and reflective activities but require visual stimuli, hands-on activities, and interactive resources to stay engaged.*
- *The school values the inclusion of diverse perspectives and the development of students' intellectual autonomy.*

Specific Needs:

- *Present the topic in a thought-provoking, critical, and accessible way.*
- *Stimulate critical thinking and ethical argumentation.*
- *Use media resources that encourage active student participation.*

Your Task:

- *Use the provided templates to document and plan the production of your Digital Educational Material.*
- *Plan your material based on the ADDIE Model and develop a Digital Educational Material that introduces and deepens the theme "Ethics and Artificial Intelligence in Education." It should promote reflection on issues such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, system transparency, and the ethical responsibility of AI developers and users.*
- *Choose appropriate technologies and media, suited to the students' profile, to create an engaging and participatory learning resource.*
- *You may use Artificial Intelligence tools to support material development (e.g., AI for image generation, video editing, or generating debate questions). If used, you must clearly identify which tools were used, at what stage, and reflect on the ethical implications of their use.*

By the end, you should be able to describe:

- *The material developed (type of media, technologies used, format).*
- *How the needs of the target audience were considered in choosing the language, media, and activities.*
- *A critical reflection on the use of Artificial Intelligence in the creation process and on the ethical approach proposed in the content.*

Figure 2 illustrates the dynamics of applying problem-situations in this course. Since the problem-situations are linked to a central theme rather than to different topics, students were able to focus on a single context. This allowed them to explore the development of various Digital Educational Materials, using distinct media formats (audio, image, video, text, etc.) and diverse digital technologies, enabling them to compare the potential of each and assess their suitability for different pedagogical objectives and target audiences — all within the same theme.

Initially, during the first in-person class, teams were formed directly within the Moodle Virtual Learning Environment (VLE), and each group selected a subtheme. In a second stage, in another class, the first problem-situation was presented, and students, based on their prior knowledge and the knowledge acquired in the course, had to develop a functional solution. This development was to be carried out by applying the ADDIE Model, but adapted specifically for the production of a digital educational material, no longer in the broader scope of an entire course or subject. After the submission of the first solution, a new problem-situation was presented.

Figure 2. Active Methodology used in the Digital Material Production course in 2025/1. The authors (2025)

3.3 Integration of Ethical and Socioemotional Transversal Competencies

Based on research cited in this article, several authors indicate that affectivity in Distance Education (DE) is directly related to academic success, student retention, and the overall quality of the educational experience. Despite technological advancements, many courses still adhere to an instructional logic centered on content transmission, neglecting dialogic mediation and student care.

When one of the authors took over the course in the first semester of 2024, a diagnostic assessment was conducted with the group, revealing a class of discontented students who resisted teamwork, complained about having to attend in-person classes, the volume of required readings, the number of assignments, the lack of time, limited familiarity with educational technologies, and a perceived lack of empathy from various stakeholders in the program, among other concerns.

After assessing the course structure, already developed within the Moodle VLE, and considering the limited time available, it was clear that a complete structural reform would not be possible. Instead, specific changes were implemented, particularly in the approach to working with the students and during the in-person sessions, which accounted for 20 hours of the total 90-hour course load. The students' progress during the 2024/1 offering was monitored, focusing on the aspects developed with the group. In subsequent offerings, through a continuous improvement process, the results culminated in the work presented here.

Thus, with a total workload of 90 hours, the course was fully developed within Moodle, aiming to ensure that graduates understand current digital technologies and their role in education, as well as the potential and systematic production of digital educational materials. The objective was to utilize both established and innovative technological resources effectively and ethically, fostering an affective and responsible approach to digital resource development.

4 Results and Discussion

In this section, the results of this work will be presented, compared to previous course offerings, along with findings from a questionnaire applied and analyzed to understand students' perspectives regarding the development of the most recent offering of the course. Below is a list of methodological changes, comparing the evolution between the first and the third offerings taught by the professor:

2024/1:

- Single theme for the production of Digital Educational Materials (DEMs), but without the structured case-scenarios. Students were responsible for choosing their target audience and did not follow a specific script.
- Traditional learning modality.
- DEMs are produced entirely online in teams.
- Responses to questions exceeding a 24-hour delay.
- Assignment corrections taking more than one week after submission.
- General feedback provided, focused on guiding students toward knowledge acquisition.
- Weekly messages and reminders sent on the eve of assignment deadlines.
- In-person classes focused only on theoretical content.
- Use of tools already familiar to students for supporting the production of digital materials.

2025/1:

- Single theme for DEM production based on specific case-scenarios.
- Use of Active Learning methodologies.
- DEM production was initiated during in-person classes and continued online in a collaborative learning environment.
- Responses to student questions provided within 24 hours.
- Assignment corrections completed within a maximum of one week after submission.

- Individualized feedback on assignments, prioritizing reinforcement of what the student did correctly, suggestions for improvement, and only afterward pointing out mistakes with guidance on how to address them.
- Weekly emails and posts in the "News Forum" providing clear, personalized instructions regarding weekly activities, along with reminders before deadlines. Messages became more personalized, using Moodle resources and a more humanized, affective writing style.
- In-person classes redesigned to incorporate welcoming activities and creativity, with and without the use of technologies.
- Teaching and application of Artificial Intelligence tools to support the planning and development of DEMs, with emphasis on ethical considerations and the importance of learning how to use AI responsibly.

The graph below illustrates the evolution of student engagement in face-to-face classes, comparing the offerings from 2024/1, 2024/2, and 2025/1. A significant increase in student involvement is observed, especially after the implementation of active learning methodologies and the introduction of affective and humanized practices both in face-to-face classes and in the virtual environment. This increase in engagement can be attributed to content personalization, the use of innovative technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), and a more welcoming and attentive approach to meeting the students' needs.

Figure 3 - Graph of Student Engagement Growth in In-Person Classes.

The first class included a moment called "Welcoming and Connection," aimed at breaking the ice in a situation where the students did not know the professor, and vice versa. This type of activity was conducted in other face-to-face classes, in smaller proportions, with different approaches, always encouraging speaking, listening, creativity, and progressively increasing the students' sense of belonging to the institution.

Affective and empathetic interactions brought the class closer together, improved the teacher-student relationship, and reduced emotional distance. In addition to constant student feedback regarding the classes and their management, a questionnaire was applied at the end of the course. Out of the 17 students, 13 responded. Some of the results are described below:

Regarding the perception of the teacher's welcoming attitude, listening, empathy, and care throughout the course, 100% of respondents stated that it was very present; 84.6% affirmed that they felt completely motivated to participate in the face-to-face classes due to the affectionate atmosphere proposed by the course; 100% of respondents stated that the affective nature of the interactions (messages, feedbacks, mediations, etc.) contributed to their increased engagement in activities in the Moodle Learning Management System (LMS); when compared to other courses in the same program, 84.6% felt a distinctive care and attention to their feelings and needs, while 15.4% felt it was the same as in other courses.

Below are some student responses to open-ended questions about the affectivity in the course:

P1: Did the affective aspect of the course contribute to your perseverance and participation throughout the course? If so, how?

- **Student 1:** Yes, the affective aspect of the course contributed greatly to my perseverance and participation. The way the professor conducted the classes, always with empathy, patience, and openness to listen, made me feel more comfortable participating and learning. This created a light and welcoming environment where I felt motivated to continue, even when difficulties arose.
- **Student 2:** Yes. The professor was able to involve the class in such a way that it even brought the students closer together.
- **Student 3:** In the weekly messages and feedback on activities.
- **Student 4:** Yes, teamwork.

P2: Leave a comment about how you felt regarding the care, empathy, and welcoming during the course. Did this make any difference in your learning experience?

Student 1: The course is very inclusive, and the professor understands the specificities of each student, valuing each individual's unique aspect and ensuring greater motivation in the classroom.

Student 2: During the course, I felt very special care from the professor, with a lot of empathy and welcoming. This made all the difference in my learning experience, as I felt respected, heard, and motivated to participate. Knowing I could count on a safe and non-judgmental environment gave me more confidence to express myself, ask questions, and truly engage in the activities.

Student 3: I felt motivated and happy. I always believed in my potential, and the professor did as well.

Student 4: It helped a lot, especially with my study routine. Even though I couldn't attend all the face-to-face classes, I never felt distant from the professor and the class.

Based on the questionnaire applied to the students, 85% stated that the central theme of the course was either highly or very motivating and challenging, while 15% rated it as moderately motivating. Regarding the skills developed through the active learning methodology used, 92% of the students reported that working with problem-solving situations stimulated their initiative, creativity, and critical thinking. When asked about the contribution of teamwork to their motivation for learning, 69% of the participants stated that it led to a significant increase, while the others indicated a positive but less impactful contribution.

Technologies using Artificial Intelligence (AI) were incorporated into the course from the first day. The entire process of analyzing the students' use of these tools was done through observation, as the goal was not to evaluate performance in a summative manner but to follow their competency development over time. It was observed that initially, students showed apprehension and insecurity, especially in creating prompts and using the available resources properly. However, they gradually learned to balance decision-making regarding when and how to use AI, understanding that its use should be intentional and critical. Discussions throughout the course consistently emphasized the ethics of using technology, the importance of prior knowledge, and the role of individual creativity. Additionally, the positive potential of Artificial Intelligence in the teaching and learning process was highlighted, reinforcing the need to understand its functioning so that, in the future, they can use it consciously and effectively in their teaching practices.

5 Conclusion

The formative experience reported in this article highlights the transformative potential of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education when integrated in a critical, ethical, and context-sensitive manner for teacher training. By incorporating the project "Potentialities of Generative AI in Education" into the Digital Material

Production course, it was possible to provide students not only with technical mastery of new digital tools but also with a reflective experience on the pedagogical, social, and emotional impacts of using these technologies. The proposal aimed to promote ethical reflections, development of socio-emotional skills, and stimulate collaborative work—key aspects for the training of educators in the contemporary digital landscape.

The course structure—intertwining theoretical foundations, active learning, collaborative practices, and ethical-socio-emotional debates—proved effective in strengthening student engagement and enhancing the quality of the educational materials produced. The increase in face-to-face class attendance, coupled with the deeper discussions around AI ethics, indicates that student-centered, hybrid approaches sensitive to the complexities of technological mediation can foster more impactful learning experiences.

In summary, the results suggest that teacher training for AI use in educational contexts should go beyond technological tool mastery. It needs to be grounded in ethical values, the strengthening of human connections, and the promotion of socio-emotional competencies that facilitate welcome, dialogue, and authorship in the educational process. This reinforces the importance of adaptive, collaborative, and contextualized pedagogical practices that recognize AI as an ally in building a more just, critical, and humanized education.

It is important to note that the methodology described here can be replicated, with modifications based on contextual particularities, for teacher training in fields such as Pedagogy, Mathematics, or Engineering. The discussions on the benefits of applying the developed methodology to this cohort do not end here. These discussions and analyses are extensive and could not be fully detailed within the scope of this article. However, they are available for further review and will be described in future works.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the institutional support of Ifes/Cefor and UnAC/Ifes, as well as the financial support of the Secretariat of Science, Technology, Innovation and Professional Education (SECTI), through the Espírito Santo Research and Innovation Support Foundation (Fapes).

References

- Amaral, G., Zuin, A. A. S., Lima, R. S. A., & Ramos, M. N. (2022). Ética na implementação da IA na Educação. *Revista Ibero-Americana de Estudos em Educação*, 17(1), 243–260. <https://doi.org/10.21723/riaee.v17i1.15737>
- Anderson, L. W.; Krathwohl, D. R.; Airasian, P. W.; Cruikshank, K. A.; Mayer, R. E.; Pintrich, P. R.; Wittrock, M. C. A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives, abridged edition. White Plains, NY: Longman, 2001.
- Becker, F., & Marques, T. B. I. (2001). Aprendizagem humana: processo de construção. *Revista Brasileira de Educação*, 16, 101–108.
- Blando, A., Nascimento, M. R. L., & Oliveira, A. L. S. (2023). Afetividade na educação superior: Um estudo de caso. *Revista Brasileira de Educação*, 28, e280026. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1413-24782023280026>.
- Borenstein, J., & Howard, A. (2021). Dimensions of legal and moral use of artificial intelligence in education. *AI and Ethics*, 1(2), 145–152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-021-00038-3>
- Deslandes, S. (2007) Pesquisa social: teoria, método e criatividade. 25a Edição, revista e atualizada. Petrópolis, RJ: Vozes.
- Franco, S. R. K., Leite, S. R., & Rosa, R. A. (2006). Aprendizagem na educação a distância: Caminhos do Brasil. *Educação & Sociedade*, 27(97), 1001–1022. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S0101-73302006000400013>.
- Gava, Tânia Barbosa Salles. O Modelo ADDIE na Construção Colaborativa de Disciplinas a Distância. *INFORMÁTICA NA EDUCAÇÃO: teoria & prática*. Porto Alegre, v. 17, n. 1, jan./jun. 2014.
- Gil, A. C., (2010). Como elaborar projeto de pesquisa. 5ª ed.
- Holmes, W., Bialik, M., & Fadel, C. (2019). *Artificial intelligence in education: Promises and implications for teaching and learning*. Boston: Center for Curriculum Redesign.
- Huang, R., Tlili, A., Chang, T.-W., Nascimbeni, F., Burgos, D., & Zhang, X. (2023). Generative artificial intelligence in education: From deceptive to disruptive. *Smart Learning Environments*, 10, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-023-00218-9>.
- Jacques, L. A., Silva, R. S. B., & Farias, C. P. (2015). Como o entendimento das emoções colabora no processo de aprendizagem das diferentes gerações no ensino online. *Revista Educação e Cultura Contemporânea*, 12(28), 42–58.

- Kieling Franco, S. R., Martins, T. G., & Silva, M. A. (2006). Educação a distância na UFRGS: Trajetória, concepção e desafios. *Revista Brasileira de Educação a Distância*, 5(1), 53–66.
- Luckin, R., Holmes, W., Griffiths, M., & Forcier, L. B. (2016). *Intelligence unleashed: An argument for AI in education*. London: Pearson.
- Marcilio, F. C. P., Rezende, A. C. B., & Leite, E. A. S. (2023). Afetividade na educação superior. *Revista Educação & Tecnologia*, 27(2), 73–88.
- Moura, D. A., Silva, J. P., & Reis, A. M. (2022). Afetividade na educação a distância: Um estudo de caso. *Revista da FAEEDBA – Educação e Contemporaneidade*, 31(62), 122–139.
- Piaget, J. (2014). *O juízo moral na criança*. São Paulo: WMF Martins Fontes.
- Silva, M. M., Andrade, G. D., & Oliveira, T. M. S. (2022). Afetividade e emoções no ensino online. *Revista Práxis Educacional*, 18(46), 1–19.
- Stake, R. (1995). *The Art of Case study research*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications.
- Trierweiler, T. E. (2024). Relação professor-aluno: A importância da afetividade na educação. *Revista Diálogo Educacional*, 24(1), 10–25. <https://doi.org/10.7213/rd.v24i1.39538>
- Vieira, M. M. S., Santos, L. S., & Costa, F. R. (2022). Afetividade e processos formativos na educação digital. *Revista EDaPECI*, 22(3), 175–192.
- Villas-Boas, V., & Sauer, L. Z. (2019). Aprendizagem ativa na educação em engenharia em tempos de Indústria 4.0. In Vanderli Fava de Oliveira (Org.), *E-book - A Engenharia e as Novas DCNs - Oportunidades para Formar Mais e Melhores Engenheiros*. Editora: LTC.
- Wallon, H. (1968). *As origens do caráter na criança*. Lisboa: Estampa.
- Zhao, Y., Xing, L., & Chen, Y. (2022). The role of artificial intelligence in the future of education: A review. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 70, 2175–2192. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-022-10148-w>